

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF THE SEROPREVALENCE OF HEPATITIS
B VIRUS INFECTION TRANSMISSION AND DANGER
ASPECTS FOR THE TRANSMISSION**¹Dr Sidra Khan, ²Dr Bilal Mahmood, ³Dr. Muhammad Haroon Afzaal¹Services Hospital Lahore²Punjab Medical College Faisalabad³House Officer DHQ Sahiwal

Article Received: April 2020

Accepted: May 2020

Published: June 2020

Abstract:

Objective: The joint war and political uncertainty in Afghanistan has led to the massive invasion of displaced persons into adjacent regions of Pakistan. This current research was led to assess the seroprevalence of hepatitis B and to recognize probable danger aspects for the transmission of hepatitis B infection amongst evacuees living in camps in all provinces of Pakistan.

Place and Duration: In the medicine department of public Hospitals in Baluchistan for one-year duration from May 2018 to April 2019.

Methods: The cross-sectional study of hepatitis B surface antigen was held in May 2018 to April 2019. We counted enrollments to arbitrarily select families in the exclusion camps in Baluchistan. An indiscriminate selection of a spouse, wife and one of their children was included in the survey. Concentrated subjects whose results from the research facilities were positive for HBsAg and those whose results remained negative for HBsAg were compared.

Results: Field workforces met with 313 families through the over-all of 920 research respondents. Examples of blood from 78 research subjects (9.4%, 96% CI 7.5-11.4) were safe for HBsAg. There were 39 spouses (13.4%, 96% CI: 8.3-15.5) and 24 wives (8.1%, 96% CI: 5.6-11.7) positive for HBsAg. Available Of the 313 children, 18 (6.7%, 96% CI 4.5-8.2) were positive for HBsAg. Receiving more than 10 infusions in earlier year enlarged the risk of HBV contamination (OR 4.6, 96% CI 2.9-7.8). The child positive for HBsAg had to have the parent who was HBsAg positive compared with a youth who was HBsAg negative (OR 6.8, 96% CI 3.0-17.6).

Conclusion: Hepatitis B is profoundly prevalent amongst Afghan exiles living in those encampments. Insecure infusion practices will endure to rise extent of the current medical issue until suitable control measures are taken. The plausibility of mother-to-child transmission underscores the need to incorporate hepatitis B inoculation as a feature of routine vaccination in the current inhabitants.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Sidra Khan,**

Services Hospital Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Sidra Khan et al, *Assessment Of The Seroprevalence Of Hepatitis B Virus Infection Transmission And Danger Aspects For The Transmission.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci., 2020; 07(06).

INTRODUCTION:

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection is an important general medical problem worldwide, and the inconvenience of HBV in people who are constantly infected is about 605,200 passages each year. HBV contagion is prevalent in some portions of the world, having a reasonable to high danger of illness in Southeast Asian countries¹⁻². In Pakistan, the pervasiveness of HBV contamination has been estimated to be in the order of 6 per cent and 12 per cent in some parts of the country. In addition, the prevalence of HBV contamination is shifting in various subgroups of the population³. The prevalence of constant HBV disease in the United States is as high as 17 per cent among displaced persons from various portions of world, with a predominant rate of hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) of 5.2 per cent among those evacuated from Afghanistan⁴. The common war and political insecurity in Afghanistan have led to an enormous convergence of the excluded in neighboring regions of Pakistan. Prior to the September 11 episode, there were just 193,500 displaced persons living in 14 camps in the Baluchistan region. The number of Afghan IDPs rose to 317,300 with the creation of new camps for exiles who had escaped to safety during the bombing of Afghanistan on 11 September 2001. Limited data on the extent of HBV contamination among Afghan exiles living in different portions of our country have been made available⁵. UNHCR found that data on patterns was needed to help plan an adequate control programme. This survey aimed to assess the seroprevalence of hepatitis B and to distinguish possible danger aspects for HBV transmission amongst evacuees living in camps in Baluchistan province, Pakistan⁶⁻⁷.

METHODOLOGY:

The cross-sectional study of hepatitis B surface antigen was led in 2018. We counted enrollments to arbitrarily select families in the exclusion camps in Baluchistan. An indiscriminate selection of a

spouse, wife and one of their children was included in the survey. Seven of these 19 encampments are called "new camps" and remained built as a result of the flood of displaced people on September 11, 2001. The remaining 13 "old camps" are being used by Afghan IDPs who have arrived since time of Russian intrusion into Afghanistan in 1983. The number of Afghanistan IDPs is around 192,300 and 129,200 in the old and innovative camps individually. To assess seroprevalence of HBsAg, the cross-sectional study remained led in November 2005. In order to recognize danger issues for HBV transmission, research participants who tested positive for HBsAg at the research center were compared to individuals who tested negative for HBsAg. Families were designated as unit of inspection to measure general extent also danger issues of HBV contamination for each subgroup inside the household. This assumption depended on the side effects of studies demonstrating a range of 5.4% to 11% of banality among various population gatherings in Pakistan. In the event that the expected equivalence index of HBsAg would be "p", which corresponds to an extreme distinction of 4% from true value (d), the accompanying recipe remained applied to obtain an example of 278 families from the people (N) of nearly 57,300 families through the stage of centrality of 6%:

$$n \frac{1}{4} = NZ2 p\delta1 _ p\delta$$

$$Z2 p\delta1 _ p\delta \delta N _ 1\delta2$$

Representing non-response and missing data, a rise of 12% gave an example of the size of 307 families. Owing to budgetary requirements, 3 persons from every family remained inspected, spouse, wife and one of its young people. Due to the presence of two distinct strata (old and new) within the exile camps in Baluchistan Province, the full size of the example was dispersed in each stratum, according to the size of their population. Each of the evacuees living in camps was enrolled through portion of a sequential number specific to every family.

Table 1 Seroprevalence of HBsAg by age set amongst Afghan migrants living in camps of Baluchistan Province, Pakistan:

Age	Total observations	Sero-prevalence (%)	HbsAg positive cases	95% CI
0—5	130	4.6	6	1.7—9.7
6—10	118	5.9	7	2.4—11.9
11—15	38	7.9	3	1.6—21.3
16—20	40	5.0	2	0.9—15.5
21—30	198	10.6	21	6.6—15.7
31—40	191	8.9	17	5.2—13.8

RESULTS:

Interviewers travelled to 315 families and met with 301 (96%) families through the over-all of 916 test respondents. Blood samples from entirely test respondents remained verified for HBsAg. Blood samples from 78 test subjects (9.4%, 96% CI 7.5-11.4) were certain for HBsAg. 39 spouses (13.4%, 96% CI 8.3-15.5) and 23 wives (8.1%, 96% CI 5.6-11.7) were positive for HBsAg. The average duration of HBsAg positive husbands remained 42 years (23-62 years), while the mean duration of HBsAg positive wives was 32 years (17-51 years). Of 311 youth, 19 (6.9%, 96% CI 4.5-8.2) were sure of their HBsAg status. The mean duration of positive youth was 7.6 years (extend 5-27 years). The age-specific HBsAg seroprevalence rates among Afghan exiles recommend that virtually all age groups were influenced and that triteness increases gradually after the age of 12 years (Table 1). A large proportion of the population examined (94%) spoke Pushto (Table 2) and had moved from various parts

of Afghanistan. The length of stay in the camps has generally changed. Most of the examination population (66%) lived in former evacuation camps, while 34% had been there for less than 4 years also were living in new IDP camps in Baluchistan (Table 2). A large proportion of married couples (91 per cent and 98 per cent separately) did not attend school (Table 2). Afghan exiles who wanted to seek treatment from private experts were certain to be HBsAg, unlike those seeking treatment at an emergency clinic or essential welfare unit in camps. For both married couples, accepting multiple infusions in earlier month otherwise receiving more than 10 infusions in the previous year was related to HBV disease. In a multivariate survey, accepting more than ten infusions in earlier year enlarged danger of HBV disease (Table 2). HBsAg-positive youth remained nearly related to a HBsAg-positive maternal associated to HBsAg-negative children (Table 2).

Table 2 Multivariate analysis of danger aspects for HBV infection amongst Afghan migrants living in camps of Baluchistan Province, Pakistan:

Danger aspects	Adjusted odds ratio	95% CI
Received >10 injections last year	3.53	1.8—6.7
Received injection for last illness	1.42	0.5—4.0
HBsAg positive child	5.70	2.0—16.5
Received treatment by private practitioner	1.82	1.0—3.5

DISCUSSION:

The seroprevalence of HBsAg amongst Afghanistan evacuees living in camps in Baluchistan was 7.9 per cent, while the prevalence among spouses, wives and children was 13.5 per cent, 8.1 per cent and 6.7 per cent, separately⁸⁻⁹. The ubiquity of HBsAg in the inhabitants depends mostly on the inclusion of hepatitis B inoculation and the frequency of dangerous repeat infusions. Absence of Hepatitis B Vaccination in Evacuees and the propensity to administer infusions for basic conditions (Table 2) are key aspects explaining this significant level (>9%) of HBsAg predominance in this Afghan evacuee population. Examination of the exits landed from various parts of the world in the United States revealed a seroprevalence of 5.2% among Afghan evacuees¹⁰⁻¹¹. Given that most of the Afghan exiles who left for the United States remained of complex financial status and likely had better human services, this may explain the almost lower estimates of HBsAg seroprevalence among the Afghan exiles who landed there¹²⁻¹³. A steady increase in HBsAg seroprevalence has been found after age 12 and more recently as prevalence begins to decline (Table 1). The steady rise in the pervasiveness of HBV infection up to the age of 41 years were found in various examinations¹⁴⁻¹⁵. The greater ubiquity among the more established age groups may be due to the gradual introduction of some of danger aspects for HBV contagion during visits.

CONCLUSION:

In summary, seroprevalence of HBsAg amongst Afghanistan IDPs living in encampments in Baluchistan is indicative of an exceptionally endemic inhabitant. Hepatitis B inoculation would be incorporated as the standard vaccination in the current population. Similarly, general preventive actions, such as welfare education sessions in the camp and repetition of safe infusions among medical service providers, especially private human service providers, would be basis for control actions in contradiction of hepatitis B contamination in the current network of exiles.

REFERENCES:

1. Kumar, Tanweer, Sahib Zada, Muhammad Irfan, Huma Batool, and Wasim Sajjad. "Serological Prevalence of Hepatitis B Virus in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan." *Pakistan Journal of Zoology* 52, no. 2 (2020): 525.
2. Mehmood, Shahid, Hassan Raza, Farhan Abid, Nouman Saeed, Hafiz Muzzammel Rehan, Safdar Javed, and Muhammad Saleem Khan. "National prevalence rate of hepatitis B and C in Pakistan and its risk factors." *Journal of Public Health* (2019): 1-14.
3. Rauf, Abdul, Zafar Ahmad, Muhammad Shafee, Muhammad Alam Mengal, Muhammad Umar, and Muhammad Ashraf. "6.

- Seroprevalence of hepatitis C virus infection in surgical patients in Quetta, Pakistan." *Pure and Applied Biology (PAB)* 7, no. 2 (2018): 455-459.
4. Al Kanaani, Zaina, Sarwat Mahmud, Silva P. Kouyoumjian, and Laith J. Abu-Raddad. "The epidemiology of hepatitis C virus in Pakistan: systematic review and meta-analyses." *Royal Society open science* 5, no. 4 (2018): 180257.
 5. Adjei, A. A., H. B. Armah, F. Gbagbo, W. K. Ampofo, I. K. E. Quaye, A. Alberti, N. Clumeck et al. "HIV infection and AIDS." *management* 4 (2020): 22.
 6. Greenaway, Christina, Iuliia Makarenko, Fozia Tanveer, and Naveed Z. Janjua. "Addressing hepatitis C in the foreign-born population: a key to hepatitis C virus elimination in Canada." *Canadian Liver Journal* 1, no. 2 (2018): 34-50.
 7. Farooq, Ahmad. "Detection and Genetic Screening of HBsAg Mutants in Blood Donors & Multi-transfused Patients of Pakistani Population." PhD diss., International Islamic University, Islamabad., 2019.
 8. Mumtaz, Ghina R., Nahla Hilmi, El Zahraa Majed, and Laith J. Abu-Raddad. "Characterising HIV/AIDS knowledge and attitudes in the Middle East and North Africa: Systematic review and data synthesis." *Global Public Health* 15, no. 2 (2020): 275-298.
 9. Chemaitelly, Hiam, Helen A. Weiss, Clara Calvert, Manale Harfouche, and Laith J. Abu-Raddad. "HIV epidemiology among female sex workers and their clients in the Middle East and North Africa: systematic review, meta-analyses, and meta-regressions." *BMC medicine* 17, no. 1 (2019): 119.
 10. Abrahamsson, Ninnie, Otilia Mårdh, and Andrew J. Amato-Gauci. "Chancroid—a rare sexually transmitted infection in the EU/EEA. Attention still needed when treating certain vulnerable groups."
 11. Mahmud, Sarwat, Zaina Al Kanaani, and Laith J. Abu-Raddad. "Characterization of the hepatitis C virus epidemic in Pakistan." *BMC infectious diseases* 19, no. 1 (2019): 809.
 12. Tariq, A., M. Adnan, A. Iqbal, S. Sadia, Y. Fan, A. Nazar, S. Mussarat et al. "Ethnopharmacology and toxicology of Pakistani medicinal plants used to treat gynecological complaints and sexually transmitted infections." *South African Journal of Botany* 114 (2018): 132-149.
 13. Zia, Afiya S. "Gender Analysis for Technical Assistance for the Balochistan Rural Development and Community Empowerment Programme." (2018).
 14. Christou, Alik. "Towards Improved Data and Understanding of Stillbirth Determinants in Low-and Middle-Income Countries: Insights from Afghanistan." (2018).
 15. Abdulmughni, Jihan, E. Mahyoub, A. Al Agabri, Y. Abdulwareth, and A. Al-Serouri. "Drug Resistant Tuberculosis: An Emerging Public Health Threat in Yemen, 2014-2016." *Iproceedings* 4, no. 1 (2018): e10532.